

Effect of temperature and solvents on ultrasonic velocity and thermodynamic parameters of cyclohexane-1,1-diylbis(2-methyl-4,1-phenylene)dibenzoate solutions

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Abstract : The present work describes physico-chemical parameters of cyclohexane-1,1-diylbis(2-methyl-4,1-phenylene)dibenzoate (MBCBZ). The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic speed (U) of pure solvents : 1,4-dioxane (DO), chloroform (CF), ethyl acetate (EA), tetrahydrofuran (THF) and MBCBZ solutions of different concentrations were investigated at four different temperatures : 298, 303, 308 and 313 K to understand the effect of solvents on molecular interactions. Various acoustical and thermodynamic parameters such as ultrasonic speed (U), adiabatic compressibility (κ_s), Rao's molar sound function (R_m), specific acoustical impedance (Z), van der Waals constant (b), internal pressure (π), viscous relaxation time (τ), free volume (V_f), intermolecular free path length (L_f) and classical absorption coefficient (α/f^2)_{cl} have been determined and correlated with concentration (C). A fairly good to excellent correlation between a given parameter and concentration is observed. Studied acoustical and thermodynamic parameters indicated existence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. Gibb's free energy of activation (ΔG^*) is found to be both concentration and temperature dependent. Both enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) are found to be concentration dependent.

Keywords : Density, viscosity, ultrasonic speed, molecular interaction.

Introduction

Bisphenols are the important constituents of plastics, epoxy resins, lacquers, etc.¹. They are useful in cancer therapy² and in manufacturing thermally stable polymers and polyester resins³. Ultrasound radiations are used in synthetic organic chemistry because it decreases reaction time, % yield increases, lowers reaction temperature, avoidance of phase transfer catalysis, etc.⁴⁻⁸. Measurements of density, viscosity and ultrasonic speed have been used to study organic liquids, liquid mixtures, and polymeric solutions⁹⁻¹⁹. Ultrasonic speed and related parameters furnish information about molecular structure, size, shape, molecular packing, molecular motion, strength of molecular interactions, and are important in processing technology. Molecular interactions result into conformational changes and hence change in the solution viscosity, osmotic pressure, light scattering, etc.

In the present work we have reported ultrasonic studies of cyclohexane-1,1-diylbis(2-methyl-4,1-phenylene)dibenzoate (MBCBZ) solutions at four different temperatures. Various acoustical and thermodynamic parameters are evaluated to understand molecular interactions in solutions of different polarity. Fig. 1 shows structure of cyclohexane-1,1-diylbis(2-methyl-4,1-phenylene)dibenzoate (MBCBZ).

Cyclohexane-1,1-diylbis(2-methyl-4,1-phenylene)dibenzoate
Molecular formula : $C_{34}H_{32}O_4$
Molar mass : 504

Fig. 1. Structure of cyclohexane-1,1-diylbis(2-methyl-4,1-phenylene)dibenzoate (MBCBZ).

Results and discussion

Density, viscosity and ultrasonic speed :

Experimentally derived quantities namely ρ , η and U of pure DO, CF, EA, THF and MBCBZ solutions at four different temperatures : 298, 303, 308 and 313 K are presented in Tables 1–2, respectively. The densities of MBCBZ solutions increased linearly with concentration (C) (except CF in which it is decreased with C) and decreased linearly with temperature. The density of CF is

greater than that of MBCBZ, so the density decreased with C in CF system. The densities of DO, EA and THF are smaller than that of MBCBZ, so ρ increased with C in these systems. Both η and U of MBCBZ solutions increased linearly with C and decreased with T . The ρ , η and U data were correlated with C and T , and excellent correlation of these parameters with C and T is found (regression coefficient $R^2 = 0.983$ – 0.999). The variation of η and U with C and T are considerably more than that

Table 1. The density (ρ), viscosity (η), and ultrasonic speed (U) data for MBCBZ in DO and CF at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K

Concentration of MBCBZ solutions (mol dm ⁻³)	DO + MBCBZ system			CF + MBCBZ system		
	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	η (m Pa s)	U (m s ⁻¹)	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	η (m Pa s)	U (m s ⁻¹)
		298 K			298 K	
0.00	1027.60	1.2227	1345.70	1478.33	0.5533	983.86
0.01	1028.15	1.2236	1347.09	1473.06	0.5541	985.68
0.02	1028.86	1.2251	1348.04	1472.70	0.5552	987.33
0.04	1030.07	1.2276	1349.84	1472.06	0.5567	990.31
0.06	1031.46	1.2298	1351.75	1471.18	0.5585	993.81
0.08	1032.77	1.2326	1353.70	1470.56	0.5602	996.98
0.10	1034.12	1.2359	1355.70	1469.79	0.5618	999.87
		303 K			303 K	
0.00	1021.82	1.0943	1323.80	1468.02	0.5270	966.84
0.01	1022.52	1.0951	1325.17	1463.58	0.5278	968.73
0.02	1023.23	1.0965	1326.26	1463.26	0.5290	970.24
0.04	1024.47	1.0984	1328.02	1462.38	0.5305	973.36
0.06	1025.87	1.1008	1330.03	1461.89	0.5321	976.75
0.08	1027.21	1.1033	1332.00	1461.35	0.5341	980.07
0.10	1028.57	1.1064	1334.13	1460.66	0.5362	983.22
		308 K			308 K	
0.00	1016.21	1.0103	1302.02	1458.23	0.5017	949.89
0.01	1016.87	1.0111	1303.44	1454.05	0.5035	951.77
0.02	1017.59	1.0125	1304.56	1453.75	0.5041	953.31
0.04	1018.85	1.0143	1306.34	1452.85	0.5063	956.36
0.06	1020.27	1.0166	1308.42	1452.53	0.5081	959.77
0.08	1021.63	1.0190	1310.42	1451.82	0.5093	963.06
0.10	1023.01	1.0221	1312.61	1451.13	0.5105	966.17
		313 K			313 K	
0.00	1010.86	0.9272	1280.37	1448.46	0.4776	933.02
0.01	1011.21	0.9280	1281.95	1444.44	0.4789	934.83
0.02	1011.93	0.9293	1282.98	1444.19	0.4800	936.49
0.04	1013.22	0.9313	1285.00	1443.75	0.4817	939.45
0.06	1014.66	0.9335	1286.92	1443.11	0.4840	942.93
0.08	1016.05	0.9358	1289.16	1442.56	0.4859	946.17
0.10	1017.44	0.9385	1291.24	1441.96	0.4876	949.34

Table 2. The density (ρ), viscosity (η), and ultrasonic speed (U) data for MBCBZ in EA and THF at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K

Concentration of MBCBZ solutions (mol dm ⁻³)	EA + MBCBZ system			THF + MBCBZ system		
	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	η (m Pa s)	U (m s ⁻¹)	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	η (m Pa s)	U (m s ⁻¹)
		298 K			298 K	
0.00	894.79	0.4274	1140.53	882.33	0.4625	1278.30
0.01	896.50	0.4287	1142.63	884.45	0.4641	1279.68
0.02	897.82	0.4298	1144.28	885.85	0.4653	1280.71
0.04	900.91	0.4320	1147.98	888.84	0.4676	1283.01
0.06	903.54	0.4339	1151.50	891.52	0.4696	1284.99
0.08	906.33	0.4361	1155.00	894.38	0.4715	1287.38
0.10	909.43	0.4388	1159.06	897.55	0.4741	1289.57
		303 K			303 K	
0.00	888.65	0.4050	1118.07	876.83	0.4474	1254.25
0.01	890.37	0.4064	1120.19	878.97	0.4489	1255.69
0.02	891.71	0.4076	1122.00	880.37	0.4500	1256.86
0.04	894.83	0.4101	1125.54	883.39	0.4520	1259.04
0.06	897.48	0.4122	1129.29	886.08	0.4543	1261.30
0.08	900.29	0.4148	1132.65	888.96	0.4568	1263.59
0.10	903.42	0.4175	1136.92	892.15	0.4598	1266.07
		308 K			308 K	
0.00	882.47	0.3846	1095.64	871.30	0.4299	1230.27
0.01	884.20	0.3858	1097.86	873.44	0.4316	1231.88
0.02	885.56	0.3870	1099.58	874.86	0.4331	1233.02
0.04	888.70	0.3892	1103.25	877.89	0.4356	1235.25
0.06	891.38	0.3912	1107.01	880.60	0.4382	1237.62
0.08	894.21	0.3935	1110.45	883.50	0.4410	1239.96
0.10	897.37	0.3963	1114.77	886.71	0.4439	1242.52
		313 K			313 K	
0.00	876.23	0.3644	1073.41	865.73	0.4129	1206.46
0.01	877.99	0.3655	1075.73	867.88	0.4149	1208.22
0.02	879.35	0.3666	1077.35	869.32	0.4164	1209.24
0.04	882.53	0.3684	1081.22	872.37	0.4192	1211.81
0.06	885.24	0.3704	1084.85	875.09	0.4217	1214.08
0.08	888.09	0.3726	1088.47	878.01	0.4245	1216.67
0.10	891.29	0.3753	1092.69	881.23	0.4273	1219.11

of ρ due to specific molecular interactions such as association, dissociation, H-bonding, etc. occurring in the solutions. Intermolecular motion in solution is affected by molecular interactions³⁷. Attractive forces result into molecular association (solvation), i.e. modification of the structure of the solute. Molecular association leads to changes in both the apparent molecular volume as well as molecular mass and hence the density of the solution. The decrease of ρ , η and U with T indicated decrease of

cohesive forces¹⁷⁻¹⁹. van der Waals, H-bonding, dipolar and London type interactions resulted into the aggregation of the solvent molecules around solute molecules and as a consequence structural modification resulted^{17-19,38}. The nature of solvent and the solute play an important role in determining all transport and other properties of the solutions. Thus, knowledge of molecular interactions is an important tool for processing technology especially from solutions.

Various acoustical and thermodynamic parameters of pure MBCBZ solutions were derived according to eqs. (1)-(13) by using ρ , η and U data at different temperatures and were correlated with C and T . The least-squares equations along with regression coefficients (R^2) are reported in Tables 3–6, from which it is observed that there is a good correlation between given parameters with C and T . Excellent correlation between above mentioned parameters with concentration and temperature is observed. Strong molecular interactions are supported by nonlinear increase of S_n with C and nonlinear decrease with T . Nonlinear variation of S_n with C further supported competing solute-solute and solvent-solute interactions with increasing solution concentrations.

Both U and Z were increased with C and decreased with T due to strong molecular interactions. κ_s of solutions is decreased with C and increased with T in all solvents. This can be attributed to fact that the solvated molecules were fully compressed by the electrical forces of the solute. The strong solvent-solute interactions lead to compressibility. The compressibility of the solution is mainly due to the free solvent molecules. Due to molecular association (solvent-solute interactions) compressibility of the solution is decreased with the increasing solute concentration. Inter molecular free path length is inversely proportional to ultrasonic speed. It was observed from the results that L_f and $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ decreased with C and increased with temperature further supported the presence of

Table 3. The least-square equations and regression coefficients for MBCBZ solutions in DO at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K

Parameter	Least square equations (regression coefficients, R^2) [DO + MBCBZ]			
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	66.04C + 1027 (0.999)	67.08C + 1021 (0.999)	68.08C + 1016 (0.999)	69.15C + 1010 (0.999)
η (m Pa s)	0.1322C + 1.2223 (0.9968)	0.1222C + 1.0938 (0.9964)	0.1171C + 1.0099 (0.9953)	0.1142C + 0.9268 (0.9984)
U (m s ⁻¹)	95.35C + 1346 (0.999)	98.51C + 1324 (0.999)	100.8C + 1302 (0.999)	102.9C + 1280 (0.999)
$Z \times 10^{-6}$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.1889C + 1.383 (0.9997)	0.1923C + 1.3529 (0.9994)	0.1938C + 1.3234 (0.9994)	0.1964C + 1.2941 (0.9992)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{10}$ (Pa ⁻¹)	-1.105C + 5.372 (0.999)	-1.1976C + 5.5822 (0.9991)	-1.2863C + 5.8023 (0.999)	-1.3893C + 6.0334 (0.9987)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	-0.5016C + 4.8528 (0.9994)	-0.5335C + 4.9469 (0.9991)	-0.5621C + 5.0435 (0.9991)	-0.5955C + 5.1429 (0.9987)
$R_m \times 10^4$ (m ^{10/3} s ^{-1/3} mol ⁻¹)	21.692C + 9.4718 (1)	21.576C + 9.4712 (1)	21.461C + 9.4708 (1)	21.345C + 9.4704 (1)
$b \times 10^5$ (m ³)	18.523C + 8.0794 (1)	18.696C + 8.1147 (1)	18.88C + 8.1498 (1)	19.062C + 8.1856 (1)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-11.267C + 5.317 (0.996)	-10.928C + 5.1369 (0.996)	-10.766C + 5.0403 (0.9959)	-10.564C + 4.9293 (0.9959)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	3.8612C + 1.0774 (0.9999)	4.4758C + 1.2418 (0.9999)	4.9462C + 1.3654 (0.9999)	5.5078C + 1.5145 (0.9999)
$\tau \times 10^{13}$ (s)	-0.8732C + 8.7551 (0.9949)	-0.8566C + 8.1412 (0.9959)	-0.8459C + 7.8132 (0.9944)	-0.8192C + 7.4562 (0.9933)
$(\alpha/f^2)_{cl} \times 10^{15}$ (s ² m ⁻¹)	-2.1925C + 12.827 (0.9971)	-2.1802C + 12.125 (0.9975)	-2.1992C + 11.831 (0.9969)	-2.1917C + 11.48 (0.9956)
S_n	-7E+06C ⁴ + 2E+06C ³ - 122697C ² + 4031.9C - 17.996 (0.9934)	-6E+06C ⁴ + 1E+06C ³ - 110058C ² + 3644.5C - 16.46 (0.9991)	-6E+06C ⁴ + 1E+06C ³ - 110150C ² + 3671.3C - 16.398 (0.9984)	-4E+06C ⁴ + 1E+06C ³ - 82888C ² + 3022.4C - 12.78 (0.9811)

Table 4. The least-square equations and regression coefficients for MBCBZ solutions in CF at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K

Parameter	Least square equations (regression coefficients, R^2) [CF + MBCBZ]			
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
ρ (kg m^{-3})	$66.04C + 1027$ (0.999)	$67.08C + 1021$ (0.999)	$68.08C + 1016$ (0.999)	$69.15C + 1010$ (0.999)
η (m Pa s)	$0.0856C + 0.5533$ (0.9989)	$0.0903C + 0.527$ (0.9972)	$0.0865C + 0.5024$ (0.9828)	$0.1001C + 0.4778$ (0.9979)
U (m s^{-1})	$95.35C + 1346$ (0.999)	$98.51C + 1324$ (0.999)	$100.8C + 1302$ (0.999)	$102.9C + 1280$ (0.999)
$Z \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	$0.191C + 1.4545$ (0.9992)	$0.1954C + 1.4194$ (0.9995)	$0.1923C + 1.3852$ (0.9995)	$0.1915C + 1.3514$ (0.9995)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{10}$ (Pa^{-1})	$-2.0127C + 6.9865$ (0.9992)	$-2.1824C + 7.2853$ (0.9996)	$-2.2991C + 7.5985$ (0.9996)	$-2.4478C + 7.9296$ (0.9997)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	$-0.8028C + 5.5343$ (0.9993)	$-0.8528C + 5.6514$ (0.9997)	$-0.8797C + 5.7716$ (0.9996)	$-0.917C + 5.896$ (0.9997)
$R_m \times 10^4$ ($\text{m}^{10/3} \text{s}^{-1/3} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$9.8878C + 8.0521$ (1)	$9.8019C + 8.0457$ (1)	$9.7188C + 8.0388$ (1)	$9.635C + 8.0303$ (1)
$b \times 10^5$ (m^3)	$8.8997C + 7.5447$ (1)	$9.0102C + 7.5864$ (1)	$9.1302C + 7.627$ (1)	$9.2508C + 7.668$ (1)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	$-4.4209C + 3.7577$ (0.999)	$-4.4123C + 3.7441$ (0.9989)	$-4.4267C + 3.732$ (0.9995)	$-4.3809C + 3.7153$ (0.9992)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m^3)	$5.9942C + 3.4913$ (0.9999)	$6.257C + 3.6595$ (0.9999)	$6.6055C + 3.8282$ (0.9992)	$6.7439C + 4.0181$ (0.9998)
$\tau \times 10^{13}$ (s)	$-0.7096C + 5.1547$ (0.9974)	$-0.682C + 5.119$ (0.9925)	$-0.6884C + 5.09$ (0.9754)	$-0.5323C + 5.0522$ (0.9943)
$(\alpha/f^2)_{cl} \times 10^{15}$ ($\text{s}^2 \text{m}^{-1}$)	$-2.9342C + 10.676$ (0.9994)	$-3.178C + 10.565$ (0.9956)	$-3.1008C + 10.439$ (0.9979)	$-3.0571C + 10.329$ (0.9987)
S_n	$-3E+06C^4 + 73141C^3$ $- 59380C^2 + 1854.4C$ $- 8.8863$ (0.9857)	$-3E+06C^4 + 730427C^3$ $- 56344C^2 + 1772.2C$ $- 8.3297$ (0.9904)	$-3E+06C^4 + 659139C^3$ $- 50932C^2 + 1617.5C$ $- 7.0903$ (0.9987)	$-3E+06C^4 + 667577C^3$ $- 50669C^2 + 1587.6C$ $- 6.946$ (0.9981)

strong molecular interactions. The presence of solvent-solute interactions can also be confirmed from dispersion of ultrasonic speed, which is characterized by relaxation process. According to Eyring rate theory τ is inversely proportional to temperature and hence, increased in the temperature of system caused to decrease in relaxation process. τ is decreased with C and T (except THF system it increased slightly with T). Rao's molar sound function (R_m) and van der Waals constant (b) increased with C and T indicated that there is no complex or aggregate formation taken place all the systems. The internal pressure (π) decreased with concentration and increased with temperature. The results of π also confirmed our observations for κ_s and L_f . A variation in the values of π is due

to different orientations of MBCBZ in DO, CF, EA and THF. The free volume (V_f) is inversely proportional to the internal pressure (π) and vice-versa. The ordered structural arrangement is due to decreasing entropy of the system. Ester and methyl groups of MBCBZ are electronegative and electropositive in nature, respectively. The lone pairs of electrons THF, DO, ester group of EA and chlorine of CF are electronegative in nature. The dipole-dipole interaction of the same type leads to structure formation, while of the opposite type leads to structure breaking tendency. Solvation phenomenon is found minimum in CF as compared to other systems. The variation in S_n with C and T also suggesting the presence of strong dipole-dipole interactions.

Table 5. The least-square equations and regression coefficients for MBCBZ solutions in EA at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K

Parameter	Least square equations (regression coefficients, R^2) [EA + MBCBZ]			
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
ρ (kg m^{-3})	$66.04C + 1027$ (0.999)	$67.08C + 1021$ (0.999)	$68.08C + 1016$ (0.999)	$69.15C + 1010$ (0.999)
η (m Pa s)	$0.1107C + 0.4275$ (0.9981)	$0.1228C + 0.4051$ (0.9992)	$0.1138C + 0.3846$ (0.9982)	$0.1059C + 0.3643$ (0.9961)
U (m s^{-1})	$95.35C + 1346$ (0.999)	$98.51C + 1324$ (0.999)	$100.8C + 1302$ (0.999)	$102.9C + 1280$ (0.999)
$Z \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	$0.3302C + 1.0208$ (0.9995)	$0.3295C + 0.9938$ (0.9994)	$0.329C + 0.9671$ (0.9994)	$0.3276C + 0.9409$ (0.9994)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{10}$ (Pa^{-1})	$-4.0027C + 8.5868$ (0.9995)	$-4.306C + 8.9965$ (0.9994)	$-4.641C + 9.4339$ (0.9994)	$-4.9903C + 9.8977$ (0.9993)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	$-1.4467C + 6.1356$ (0.9995)	$-1.5209C + 6.2802$ (0.9994)	$-1.6013C + 6.4311$ (0.9994)	$-1.6815C + 6.5873$ (0.9994)
$R_m \times 10^4$ ($\text{m}^{10/3} \text{s}^{-1/3} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$26.141C + 10.3$ (0.9999)	$25.963C + 10.297$ (0.9999)	$25.786C + 10.295$ (0.9999)	$25.61C + 10.292$ (1)
$b \times 10^5$ (m^3)	$23.075C + 9.2035$ (0.9999)	$23.35C + 9.2532$ (0.9999)	$23.63C + 9.3038$ (0.9999)	$23.915C + 9.3555$ (0.9999)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	$-7.0927C + 3.1105$ (0.9948)	$-7.0469C + 3.0951$ (0.9948)	$-7.0694C + 3.0821$ (0.9946)	$-7.0784C + 3.065$ (0.9944)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m^3)	$16.287C + 4.0574$ (1)	$16.822C + 4.2782$ (1)	$17.887C + 4.4855$ (1)	$19.049C + 4.7179$ (1)
$\tau \times 10^{13}$ (s)	$-1.072C + 4.8952$ (0.9995)	$-0.9219C + 4.8599$ (0.9983)	$-1.0187C + 4.8387$ (0.9979)	$-1.096C + 4.8091$ (0.9947)
$(\alpha/f^2)_{cl} \times 10^{15}$ ($\text{s}^2 \text{m}^{-1}$)	$-3.5087C + 8.8324$ (0.9977)	$-3.2678C + 8.7069$ (0.9988)	$-2.9934C + 8.5698$ (0.9989)	$-3.1566C + 8.4621$ (0.9997)
S_n	$-5E+06C^4 + 1E+06C^3$ $- 82255C^2 + 2431.2C$ $- 11.191$ (0.9839)	$-5E+06C^4 + 1E+06C^3$ $- 77714C^2 + 2336.1C$ $- 10.642$ (0.9681)	$-5E+06C^4 + 1E+06C^3$ $- 78473C^2 + 2322.1C$ $- 10.288$ (0.9895)	$-5E+06C^4 + 1E+06C^3$ $- 74041C^2 + 2242C$ $- 9.4809$ (0.9728)

When ultrasonic waves are incident on the solution, the molecules get perturbed and as a result both ultrasonic speed and intermolecular free path length are affected. Since the medium has some elasticity and hence perturbed molecules regain their equilibrium positions. When a solute is added to a solvent, its molecules attract certain solvent molecules toward them. The phenomenon is known as compression and also as limiting compressibility. The aggregation of solvent molecules around solute molecules supports strong solvent-solute interactions and considerable change in structural arrangement. Molecular interactions such as solvent-solute interactions, quantum mechanical dispersive forces and dielectric force may cause high degree of contraction or expansion. The time

lag between the excitation and de-excitation processes is observed as an acoustical relaxation. This relaxation process is observed as either an increase in speed with frequency or a decrease in the $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ with frequency.

Increasing temperature has two opposite effects namely structure formation (intermolecular association) and structure destruction. The structure forming tendency is primarily due to solvent-solute interactions, while destruction of structure formed previously is due to thermal fluctuations. When thermal energy is greater than that of interaction energy, it causes destruction of the structure formed previously¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Dipole-dipole interactions of the opposite type favor structure formation, while of the same

Table 6. The least-square equations and regression coefficients for MBCBZ solutions in THF at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K

Parameter	Least square equations (regression coefficients, R^2) [THF + MBCBZ]			
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
ρ (kg m^{-3})	$66.04C + 1027$ (0.999)	$67.08C + 1021$ (0.999)	$68.08C + 1016$ (0.999)	$69.15C + 1010$ (0.999)
η (m Pa s)	$0.1118C + 0.4629$ (0.9966)	$0.1196C + 0.4474$ (0.9959)	$0.1366C + 0.4301$ (0.999)	$0.1399C + 0.4134$ (0.9975)
U (m s^{-1})	$95.35C + 1346$ (0.999)	$98.51C + 1324$ (0.999)	$100.8C + 1302$ (0.999)	$102.9C + 1280$ (0.999)
$Z \times 10^{-6}$ ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	$0.2887C + 1.1285$ (0.9988)	$0.2898C + 1.1004$ (0.9988)	$0.29C + 1.0726$ (0.9986)	$0.2909C + 1.0452$ (0.9986)
$\kappa_s \times 10^{10}$ (Pa^{-1})	$-2.3132C + 6.9305$ (0.9988)	$-2.5061C + 7.2437$ (0.9988)	$-2.7061C + 7.5758$ (0.9985)	$-2.9339C + 7.9276$ (0.9983)
$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	$-0.9275C + 5.5121$ (0.9988)	$-0.9832C + 5.6352$ (0.9988)	$-1.0383C + 5.763$ (0.9986)	$-1.1008C + 5.8953$ (0.9984)
$R_m \times 10^4$ ($\text{m}^{10/3} \text{s}^{-1/3} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$28.822C + 8.8723$ (0.9999)	$28.643C + 8.873$ (0.9999)	$28.469C + 8.8737$ (0.9999)	$28.296C + 8.8743$ (0.9999)
$b \times 10^5$ (m^3)	$24.873C + 7.6447$ (0.9999)	$25.145C + 7.6816$ (0.9999)	$25.424C + 7.719$ (0.9999)	$25.709C + 7.7571$ (0.9999)
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	$-10.692C + 3.8442$ (0.9923)	$-10.648C + 3.8381$ (0.9922)	$-10.643C + 3.8306$ (0.9919)	$-10.57C + 3.8116$ (0.9925)
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m^3)	$16.237C + 3.1668$ (0.9998)	$16.559C + 3.2394$ (1)	$16.864C + 3.34$ (0.9999)	$17.398C + 3.4431$ (0.9999)
$\tau \times 10^{13}$ (s)	$-0.1911C + 4.37$ (0.975)	$-0.2205C + 4.3454$ (0.9828)	$-0.3793C + 4.3221$ (0.9728)	$-0.4284C + 4.2777$ (0.9935)
$(\alpha/f^2)_{cl} \times 10^{15}$ ($\text{s}^2 \text{m}^{-1}$)	$-1.0359C + 7.141$ (0.9976)	$-1.0201C + 6.9635$ (0.9964)	$-1.2129C + 6.7941$ (0.9928)	$-1.2245C + 6.5979$ (0.9977)
S_n	$-7E+06C^4 + 2E+06C^3$ $- 116944C^2 + 3724.9C$ $- 18.045$ (0.9816)	$-6E+06C^4 + 1E+06C^3$ $- 106299C^2 + 3481.5C$ $- 16.393$ (0.9556)	$-6E+06C^4 + 1E+06C^3$ $- 105165C^2 + 3400.1C$ $- 15.28$ (0.9818)	$-5E+06C^4 + 1E+06C^3$ $- 86457C^2 + 2975C$ $- 11.772$ (0.9591)

type favor structure breaking tendency. The decreasing cohesive forces lead to increasing free length and free volume of the system.

Thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^* were determined according to eqs. (12) and (13) using viscous relaxation time data as a function of concentration and temperature are shown in Tables 7–10. The linear variation of ΔG^* with C also indicates that the absorption is due to rearrangement of molecules independent on concentration (see Figs. 2–5). In DO system ΔG^* decreased with increasing C ($R^2 = 0.997$ – 0.999) and decreased with increasing T , while both ΔH^* and ΔS^* increased with increasing C . In EA and CF systems ΔG^* decreased with increasing C ($R^2 = 0.987$ – 0.999) and in-

Fig. 2. The plots of Gibbs energy of activation (ΔG^*) against concentration (C) for MBCBZ in DO at 298 K (\blacklozenge), 303 K (\blacksquare), 308 K (\blacktriangle) and 313 K (\times).

Fig. 3. The plots of Gibbs energy of activation (ΔG^*) against concentration (C) for MBCBZ in CF at 298 K (◆), 303 K (■), 308 K (▲) and 313 K (×).

Fig. 5. The plots of Gibbs energy of activation (ΔG^*) against concentration (C) for MBCBZ in THF at 298 K (◆), 303 K (■), 308 K (▲) and 313 K (×).

Fig. 4. The plots of Gibbs energy of activation (ΔG^*) against concentration (C) for MBCBZ in EA at 298 K (◆), 303 K (■), 308 K (▲) and 313 K (×).

increased with increasing T , while both ΔH^* and ΔS^* are found approximately independent of C . In THF system ΔG^* decreased with increasing C ($R^2 = 0.996-0.999$)

and increased with increasing T . Both ΔH^* and ΔS^* increased with increasing C . Derived thermodynamic parameters indicated that condensation and evaporation processes are found concentration and temperature dependent. The negative values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* indicated that activated complexes are in ordered state, i.e. condensation process is predominant over evaporation process, which is further supported by positive values of S_n with C . Thus, thermodynamic parameters supported presence of strong molecular interactions occurring in the solutions of different polarity.

Experimental

Materials :

The solvents and chemicals used in the present investigation were of AR grade and were further purified according to literature methods²⁰. Cyclohexane-1,1-diylbis(2-methyl-4,1-phenylene)dibenzoate used in this study was synthesized in our laboratory. Purity of the cyclohexane-

Table 7. Thermodynamic parameters (ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^*) derived using τ data for MBCBZ in 1,4-dioxane solutions

System	ΔG^* (J mol ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K		
DO + MBCBZ	4192.4	4189.5	4126.4	4111.0	5.60	4.74
	4190.4	4186.9	4123.6	4108.5	5.61	4.83
	4185.8	4181.5	4118.0	4102.7	5.63	4.91
	4180.0	4175.9	4112.1	4097.5	5.65	4.99
	4175.3	4170.7	4107.0	4091.1	5.66	5.08
	4171.5	4166.3	4102.6	4086.8	5.67	5.16

Table 8. Thermodynamic parameters (ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^*) derived using τ data for MBCBZ in chloroform solutions

System	ΔG^* (J mol ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K		
CF + MBCBZ	2878.3	2999.5	3028.5	3098.9	-1.55	-14.85
	2876.3	2998.4	3024.6	3097.0	-1.54	-14.80
	2869.2	2990.5	3020.6	3091.5	-1.60	-14.99
	2861.1	2982.0	3012.9	3086.0	-1.66	-15.14
	2854.6	2975.6	3003.3	3079.9	-1.65	-15.09
	2848.8	2970.9	2994.6	3073.3	-1.62	-14.97

Table 9. Thermodynamic parameters (ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^*) derived using τ data for MBCBZ in ethyl acetate solutions

System	ΔG^* (J mol ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K		
EA + MBCBZ	2748.7	2865.5	2895.6	2966.6	-1.63	-14.67
	2744.0	2861.2	2891.5	2962.9	-1.65	-14.73
	2732.3	2851.6	2879.7	2947.7	-1.58	-14.48
	2720.8	2840.4	2868.2	2935.7	-1.58	-14.44
	2710.7	2832.9	2858.8	2925.8	-1.59	-14.42
	2700.0	2821.4	2848.1	2915.1	-1.60	-14.43

Table 10. Thermodynamic parameters (ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^*) derived using τ data for MBCBZ in tetrahydrofuran solutions

System	ΔG^* (J mol ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K		
THF + MBCBZ	2416.9	2568.5	2613.0	2722.5	-3.56	-20.07
	2415.7	2565.5	2612.6	2723.2	-3.65	-20.37
	2410.8	2559.7	2606.5	2720.4	-3.76	-20.69
	2405.9	2555.3	2602.2	2717.6	-3.81	-20.86
	2398.9	2552.0	2598.7	2715.3	-3.91	-21.17
	2395.5	2549.7	2596.2	2712.4	-3.92	-21.19

1,1-diylbis(2-methyl-4,1-phenylene)dibenzoate was checked by aluminum coated TLC plates 60 F245 (E. Merck) and was crystallized four times from ethyl acetate. 1,4-Dioxane (DO), chloroform (CF), ethyl acetate (EA) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were supplied by Spectrochem Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. The estimated purity of solvents was more than 0.99–0.994 mole fraction and 0.995 mole fraction by Gas chromatographic analysis

(values provided by the manufacturer) and was confirmed by HPLC. Certified purities and water content measurement by Karl-Fischer of all solvents are given in Table 11. The density, viscosity and ultrasonic speed of pure solvents were compared with the literature values²¹⁻³¹ and are shown in Table 12. 1,4-Dioxane (DO) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were distilled on a 3-ft long fractionation column after being refluxed overnight on so-

Table 11. Chemicals used in this work

Chemicals	Prod. No.	Mole fraction purities		Water content (by manufacturer)	Water content (obtained by KF)
		(by manufacturer)	(obtained by GC)		
1,4-Dioxane	010460	0.995	0.995	0.1%	0.09%
Chloroform	010333	0.994	0.993	0.05%	0.05%
Ethyl acetate	010520	0.995	0.994	0.1%	0.09%
Tetrahydrofuran	0120100	0.995	0.995	0.1%	0.09%
MBCBZ	-	-	0.990	-	0.08%

Table 12. Comparison of measured density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) data for pure DO, CF, EA and THF with literature values at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K

T (K)	ρ (kg m ⁻³)		η (m Pa s)		U (m s ⁻¹)	
	Expt.	Lit.	Expt.	Lit.	Expt.	Lit.
	DO					
298	1027.60	1027.99 ^a	1.2227	1.212 ^a	1345.70	1345.1 ^a
303	1021.82	1022.33 ^a	1.0943	1.115 ^a	1323.80	1323.1 ^a
308	1016.21	1016.36 ^a	1.0103	1.028 ^a	1302.02	1301.3 ^a
313	1010.46	1010.97 ^a	0.9272	0.952 ^a	1280.37	1279.7 ^a
CF						
298	1478.33	1478.8 ^b 1446.1 ^c 1478.9 ^e	0.5533	0.576 ^b 0.545 ^c	983.86	984 ^e
303	1468.02	1469.2 ^b 1451.3 ^c 14692.1 ^d	0.5270	0.552 ^b 0.534 ^c 0.534 ^d	966.84	969 ^d
308	1458.23	1432.5 ^c	0.5017	0.498 ^c	949.89	
313	1448.46	1450.0 ^b 14497.4 ^d	0.4776	0.509 ^b 0.491 ^d	933.02 934 ^d	
EA						
298	894.79	894.81 ^f 894.6 ^g	0.4274	0.421 ^f 0.424 ^g	1140.53	1137.7 ^h
303	888.65	887.14 ^f 888.5 ^g	0.4050	0.399 ^f 0.400 ^g	1118.07	1115.3 ^h
308	882.47	882.21 ^f 882.5 ^g	0.3846	0.381 ^f 0.385 ^g	1095.64	1093.0 ^h
313	876.23	878.92 ^f	0.3644	0.363 ^f	1073.41	1070.7 ^h
THF						
298	882.33	882.50 ⁱ 882.01 ^j	0.4625	0.4593 ⁱ 0.449 ^j	1278.30	1278.24 ^j
303	876.83	877.0 ^k	0.4474	0.42 ^k	1254.25	1254.00 ^k
308	871.30		0.4299		1230.27	
313	865.73	865.93 ⁱ 861.2 ^k	0.4129	0.4007 ⁱ 0.39 ^k	1206.46	1202.00 ^k

^aReference [21]. ^bReference [22]. ^cReference [23]. ^dReference [24]. ^eReference [25]. ^fReference [26]. ^gReference [27].

^hReference [28]. ⁱReference [29]. ^jReference [30]. ^kReference [31].

dium-potassium alloy. It was found that traces of moisture do not affect their dielectric constant or solvating power and contribute only insignificantly to their conductance. In view of this, the investigation was carried out in a closed system but not on a high-vacuum line. Ethyl acetate was kept over anhydrous K₂CO₃ for more than 72 h²⁰ and was fractionally distilled twice. The middle fraction of the distillate was used. Chloroform was shaken

several times with distilled water to remove ethanol. It was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and then fractionally distilled. Distilled water of conductivity range 3–5 × 10⁻⁶ S cm⁻¹ at 25 °C was distilled with the help of Millipore (Elix) distillation unit, this water was further distilled in the presence of alkaline potassium permanganate through a (750 mm) long vertical fractionating column. The water so obtained has conductance value ≈1–4

$\times 10^{-7}$ S cm⁻¹ at 25 °C and pH in the range 6.5–7.0. Water of these specifications was used for all experiments.

Measurements :

A 0.1 mol MBCBZ fresh stock solutions were prepared in different solvents at room temperature. From the stock solutions a series of dilute solutions ranging from 0.01 to 0.001 mol were prepared and thermally equilibrated at specified temperatures prior to density, viscosity and ultrasonic speed measurements.

The ρ and U measurements were carried out on a Density and Sound Velocity Meter (DSA-5000 M) supplied by Anton Paar GmbH, Graz, Austria. The manufacturer claims the repeatability in density, ultrasonic speed, and temperature measurements are $\pm 1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ kg m⁻³, $\pm 1 \cdot 10^{-1}$ m s⁻¹ and $\pm 1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ K, respectively. The standard uncertainties for the density, sound velocity, and temperatures were better than $2.9 \cdot 10^{-2}$ kg m⁻³, $1.3 \cdot 10^{-1}$ m s⁻¹, and $1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ K, respectively. The calibration of DSA was done over a temperature range from 25–40 °C. DSA was thermostated within ± 0.002 °C with Peltier heating device. Viscometric measurements were carried out by using Ubbelohde suspended type viscometer. The manufacturer suggests the repeatability in the viscosity measurements is $\pm 0.1\%$. The viscosity measurements were repeated at least three times for each sample. A constant temperature bath (Nova Instruments, Ahmedabad, Model NV8550E) with an accuracy of ± 0.1 K was used for maintaining constant temperature during viscosity measurements. The flow times of pure solvents and solutions were measured with a digital RACER HS 10W stop watch with an accuracy of ± 0.01 s. The solutions were prepared by mass using an analytical balance (AB 204-S; Mettler Toledo, Switzerland) with an uncertainty of $\pm 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ kg. The mole fraction of each mixture was obtained with an uncertainty of $\pm 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ from the measured masses of the components, and all the mixtures were completely miscible over the whole composition range.

The final purities of the solvents were also confirmed by Perkin-Elmer 8410 gas chromatograph equipped with 60/80 carboxisieve S-II packed column (5 ft long, 0.125 mm i.d.) with 100 mL/min N₂ flow rate, initial column temperature 125 °C and a flame ionization detector, and

matched with manufacturer data. No molar fraction impurity higher than $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ was observed. A Karl-Fischer titration (Micro aqua cal50, Analab Scientific Inst. Pvt. Ltd., Vadodara) was used to determine the water content in all solvents.

Data processing :

Various acoustical and thermodynamic parameters were determined according to following theoretical equations :

Specific acoustical impedance (Z) :

$$Z = U\rho \quad (1)$$

Adiabatic compressibility (κ_s) :

Adiabatic compressibility (κ_s) can be evaluated according to Newton and Laplace :

$$\kappa_s = \frac{1}{U^2\rho} \quad (2)$$

Internal pressure (π)³² :

$$\pi = b'RT \left(\frac{K\eta}{U} \right)^{1/2} \frac{\rho^{2/3}}{M^{7/6}} \quad (3)$$

where b' is the packing factor (2) and K is a constant (4.28×10^9). R is the gas constant $\{8.3143/(\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1})\}$.

Free volume (V_f)³² :

$$V_f = \left[\frac{MU}{K\eta} \right]^{3/2} \quad (4)$$

Inter molecular free path length (L_f)³³ :

$$L_f = K(\kappa_s)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where K is the Jacobson's constant [$K = (93.875 + 0375T) \times 10^{-8}$] and it is temperature dependent.

van der Waals constant (b)³⁴ :

$$b = \frac{M}{\rho} \left[1 - \left[\frac{RT}{MU^2} \right] \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{MU^2}{3RT}} - 1 \right] \right] \quad (6)$$

where M is the apparent molecular weight of the solution, R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature.

Viscous relaxation time (τ) :

The resistance offered by viscous force in the flow of sound wave appears as a classical absorption associated

with it is the viscous relaxation time :

$$\tau = \frac{4\eta}{3\rho U^2} \quad (7)$$

Classical absorption coefficient $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ ³⁵ :

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{f^2}\right)_{cl} = \frac{8\pi^2\eta}{3U^3\rho} \quad (8)$$

Rao's molar sound function (R) ³⁶ :

$$R = \frac{M}{\rho} U^{1/3} \quad (9)$$

Solvation number (S_n) :

$$n = \left[1 - \frac{\kappa_s(100-X)}{\kappa_{s1}X} \right] \quad (10)$$

where X is the number of grams of solute in 100 g of the solution.

The solvation number (S_n) can be expressed as :

$$S_n = \frac{M_2}{M_1 \left(1 - \frac{\kappa_s}{\kappa_{s1}} \right) \left(\frac{100-X}{X} \right)} \quad (11)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are the molecular weights of solvent and solute, respectively.

Thermodynamic parameters :

Free energy of activation (ΔG^*), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) can be determined by using viscous relaxation time data at different concentrations and temperatures :

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \frac{kT}{h} e^{-\frac{\Delta G^*}{RT}} \quad (12)$$

$$\ln \frac{1}{\tau T} = \ln \frac{k}{h} + \frac{\Delta S^*}{R} - \frac{\Delta H^*}{RT} \quad (13)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant and h is the Planck's constant.

Conclusions

A fairly good to excellent correlation between studied parameters with concentration and temperature was ob-

served. Derived acoustical and thermodynamic parameters confirmed existence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions, which found to depend on molecular structure of the compound. ΔG^* is observed to be both concentration and temperature dependent, while both ΔH^* and ΔS^* are observed to be concentration dependent.

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